

The Description of Information System Analysis and Design (September 2021)

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Abstract— A system can be defined as elements that relate to each other to serve the same purpose. Furthermore, in developing a system requires the involvement of four components, namely input, processing, output, and feedback or control. Systems analysis is a challenging profession as it combines many skills such as analytical, technical, interpersonal and managerial skills. Current technological developments are very useful in solving problems in various fields. the process of unraveling a subject and investigating the actual situation in an entity or to look for indications of important components and elements in building an information system. Information systems can facilitate the management of raw data into information. An effective and well-implemented information system will affect the performance of management in controlling the production system of the manufacturing industry. However, information systems that are too complex and complicated can reduce the efficiency of the overall production system. In this journal, we will discuss the analysis techniques and system design on computerized or manual systems so that they are able to describe system concepts and make analysis about them.

Index Terms— System, Information System, Analysis, System Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

INFORMATION system analysis and design is one of the compulsory subjects in semester 5 at the Department of Industrial Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Andalas University. This course discusses material about systems analysis and engineering designing on a computerized system or still manual so it can describe the system concepts and analysis.

Information systems are designed to simplify the management of company data, and make all work more effective and efficient. The effectiveness and efficiency of information systems is a key aspect that can determine the progress or decline of an organization. Manufacturing industry organizations cannot be separated from this. An effective and properly implemented information system will affect the management's performance in controlling the production system of the manufacturing industry. However, information systems that are too complex and complicated can reduce the efficiency of the overall production system.[1] One of the conveniences that will be provided through this information

system is in finding information about an item because all item data will be recorded for inclusion in the database so that finding information on an item will be easy and fast.

The purpose of this journal is to describe in general the analysis and design of information systems so that readers get an overview of this material.

II. LITERATUR REVIEW

This chapter will discuss about the literatur in information system analysis and design course.

A. Definition

The system is a network of related procedures. get together to do an activity or to complete a specific target, the system can also defined as a collection of elements that interact with each other to achieve a certain goal. [2] The system is a group of elements that are integrated with the intent the same to achieve a goal. The system consists of structures and process. The structure of the system is the elements that make up the system, while the system process explains how each element of the system works in achieving system goals.[3]

While information is data that has been processed into a form that more useful and more meaningful to those who accept it.[2] Information can be defined as data that has been processed in such a way thereby increasing knowledge someone who uses the data.[3]

It can be concluded that the information system is a mutually related to each other, created by human consisting of components within the organization to achieve a purpose is to provide information. Information system is a process which performs the function of collecting, processing, storing, analyzing, and disseminate information for the purpose of specific one. Information system terms often associated with the term system management information, but both things it's actually not the same. System management information is wrong one type of information system that specifically intended to produce information for management and to make a decision.[3]

The design is carried out according to system requirements marketing information taking into account the flow of data and information on the designed system. For example, database design consists of files with linked records relate to a particular subject. Collection of records consists of fields that are

interconnected with logic. The preparation of the data structure of a database is determined by the model data used. A data model is a collection of tools or symbols used to describe data conceptually.[5]

B. Purpose

Main function of information is to increase knowledge or reduce user uncertainty information.[3]

The information value is based on ten properties, namely Information can be defined:

1. Easy to get This trait shows the ease and information can be obtained quickly.
2. Spacious and complete This trait shows the complete content information, not only about volume but also about the information output.
3. Accuracy This trait is related to the level of freedom from error output information.
4. Compatibility This trait shows how good output information in relation at the request of the users.
5. Punctuality This trait is related to time passed for input, processing, and reporting output to shorter users than the cycle to get information.
6. Clarity This property indicates the level of output information that is free from terms which is not clear.
7. Dexterity This trait is related to being able to customized information output not only with more than one decision.
8. Can be proven This trait shows ability multiple users of information for test the output and arrive at the same conclusion.
9. No prejudice This trait is related to not there is a desire to change information to get the conclusions that have been previously considered.
10. Measurable This trait shows the essence information generated from the system formal information.[3]

The purpose of information systems analysis is to design new systems or improve existing systems. can make it easier to make decisions if the current system is problematic or not functioning properly & the results of the analysis will be used as a basis for improving the system.

The purpose of System Design is to determine the right amount of information, make efforts to standardize, develop control systems, and reduce duplicate functions.

C. Data Flow Diagrams (DFD)

According to Hartono DFD or data flow diagrams are: a diagram that describes the flow of data in a system using symbol notation. DFD can also shows the relationship between system components. Symbol used to make it easier for readers to see differences between processes, and data storage.

Level 0 or context diagram describes all entities into and out of the whole system, this diagram is the highest level in the DFD. On the level 0 diagram no there may be a storage component (store), there is only one process. The scope of a system can be described at the level this. The detailed diagram

is a description of the processes that exist in the diagram of a process.[4]

D. Data Dictionary

Data dictionary is a collection of data and fact information of an information system in accordance with the needs. Data dictionary stores usernames, types of access allowed, the data item and the name of the data item in the database for perform the inspection. While data dictionary can store the size and type of data items, data item constraints, and the name of the item in the data integrity check.

Data Dictionary consists of various kinds, namely: alias or pseudonym, the name of the data flow that flows in the DFD, the current data from or to the process, the explanation used to explain the existing information, the form of the data whether in the form of files, print outs or reports, data structures For example, current data consists of anything that is stored in the data dictionary, period and volume[4]

E. ERD

Entity Relationship Diagram or also called ER diagram used in documenting user requirements and in logically designing databases using ER or semantic object according to company policy [8]. ER contains a complete collection of entities with a number of attributes and a number of relational components. The symbol is divided of two symbols, namely: attributes, entities, relationships, and links. Attribute describes the purpose of the relationship or entity. Entity or An entity is a set of real or unreal objects where the data is stored, usually an entity called noun. Relationships, usually named with the verb dan is a relationship that exists between a set of entities. Link, is a liaison between entities with their relationships and attributes.[4]

F. Database Design

Database design is a process that produces a detailed data model of the database, database design involves selecting: columns for each table and how tables and columns interact with each other [9]. Term database design can function as an application of the whole design process, not just the structure database, but also queries and forms that have functions as part of the overall database within a database management system.[4]

III. DISCUSSION

In simple terms the basic concept of the system can be interpreted as a collection or set of elements, components or variables that organized, interacting, interdependent on each other and integrated. There are two groups of approaches in defining system, among others, emphasizes the procedure and some emphasizes its elements or components. The systems approach more emphasis on the procedure of defining the system as a network on procedures that are interconnected, gathered together to do an activity or to complete a certain target.

A system have certain characteristics or properties, which characterize that it can be said as a system. The characteristics in question are:

- a. System Components A system consists of a number of interrelated components interact, which work together to form a single unit.
- b. System Boundary (Boundary) The scope of the system is the limiting area between systems with other systems or systems with their external environment.
- c. External Environment (Environment) Any form that is outside the scope or limitations of the applicable system affect the operation of the system is called the external environment system.
- d. System Connector (Interface) Media that connects the system with other subsystems is called with a system interface or interface.
- e. Enter System (Input) The energy entered into the system is called the system input, which is can be in the form of maintenance (maintenance input) and signal (signal input).
- f. System Output (Output) The results of the energy that are processed and classified into outputs that are useful, this output is an input for other subsystems.
- g. System Processor A system can have a process that will change the input into output.
- h. System Goal A system has definite goals and objectives and is deterministic. If a system does not have a target, then the operation system is useless.

Stages in System Analysis:

1. Determine precisely the target system Systems analysts should conduct checks on policies and data processing procedures and information systems applied at this time called the preventive system.
2. Studying Organizational Forms Conduct a study of the organization including organizational chart, job description, studying the ongoing data flows, relationships and interrelationships between functions and jobs within the organization as well as external influences on the company's internal systems.
3. Analyzing reports that are currently generated Analyst on timeliness and reports, payload data less, the number and frequency of reports generated.
4. Conduct research on the implementation of systems and procedures currently running Analysis of implementation policies and procedures data processing, both manual and computerized.
5. Identify input data System analysis must study the input data that will later be used will greatly affect the quality of the information.
6. Evaluate the effectiveness of the current system Making conclusions on the analysis of the effectiveness of the present system and The analyst provides several alternative system options, with all possible reviews of the possibilities that occur, both its advantages and disadvantages.

IV. CONCLUSSION

Based on the explanation from this journal, it can be concluded that:

1. Analysis is an activity that starts from the initial process in study and evaluate a form existing problems.
2. System is the relationship of one unit with other units that are mutually relate to each other and which cannot separated and into a single unit in the framework of achieve the goals that have been set
3. Information is data that has been classified or processed or processed interpret for use in the process decision making
4. System Analysis is the decomposition of a complete information system into in its component parts with the intention of to identify and evaluate problems, opportunities, obstacles that occur and expected needs so that it can be proposed repair.
5. The analysis stage is carried out after the system planning stage and before system design stage. This stage is a critical and very important stage important, because an error in this stage causes an error in the the next step.

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